

Netherlands Food and Consumer
Product Safety Authority
Ministry of Agriculture,
Nature and Food Quality

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To the Head of Agency of the Netherlands Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority

Advice of the Director of the Office for Risk Assessment & Research

Advice on the implementation of the National Residues Plan Part 4: additional advice on residues in aquaculture, farmed game, rabbit and honey.

Office for Risk Assessment & Research

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Background

The National Residues Plan (NPR) in products of animal origin is the Dutch elaboration of Directive 96/22/EC¹ and the former Directive 96/23/EC². This Directive specifies which groups of substances the Member States are required to include in their annual monitoring of animal products. As such, the NPR is an important cornerstone for the free movement of animal products within the EU and for the export of animal products outside the EU. On 14 December 2019, Directive 96/23/EC will be repealed and replaced by Regulation EU 2017/625³. In addition to the specified compulsory controls, this new regulation offers more space for additional risk-based controls by the Member States.

In 2017, the Office for Risk Assessment and Research (BuRO) commissioned WFSR⁴ to develop an approach that can be used to structure the NPR in a risk-oriented manner. There are different ways of prioritising possible (chemical) food safety risks. A quantitative analysis of individual substances requires both time and budget, which are often only available to a limited extent (van Asselt et al., 2013; van der Fels-Klerx et al., 2015; Van der Fels-Klerx et al., 2018). Decision trees or expert judgement appear to be the best alternatives for prioritising (chemical) substances with regard to food safety risks; this provides sufficient differentiation between substances on the basis of available data. For the

¹ Council Directive 96/22/EC of 29 April 1996 concerning the prohibition on the use in livestock farming of certain substances having a hormonal or thyreostatic action and of β -agonists, and repealing Directives 81/602/EEC, 88/146/EEC and 88/299/EEC

² Council Directive 96/23/EC on measures to monitor certain substances and residues thereof in live animals and animal products and repealing Directives 85/358/EEC and 86/469/EEC and Decisions 89/187/EEC and 91/664/EEC.

³ Regulation (EU) 2017/625 on official controls and other official activities performed to ensure the application of food and feed law, rules on animal health and welfare, plant health and plant protection products, amending Regulations (EC) No 999/2001, (EC) No 396/2005, (EC) No 1069/2009, (EC) No 1107/2009, (EU) No 1151/2012, (EU) No 652/2014, (EU) 2016/429 and (EU) 2016/2031 of the European Parliament and of the Council, Council Regulations (EC) No 1/2005 and (EC) No 1099/2009 and Council Directives 98/58/EC, 1999/74/EC, 2007/43/EC, 2008/119/EC and 2008/120/EC, and repealing Regulations (EC) No 854/2004 and (EC) No 882/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council, Council Directives 89/608/EEC, 89/662/EEC, 90/425/EEC, 91/496/EEC, 96/23/EC, 96/93/EC and 97/78/EC and Council Decision 92/438/EEC (Official Controls Regulation).

⁴ Wageningen Food Safety Research, up to 1-6-2019 RIKILT. RIKILT merged with the Laboratory for Feed and Food Safety of the Netherlands Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority (NVWA) under the name [Wageningen Food Safety Research](#) (WFSR).

prioritisation of substances, WFSR designed decision trees according to which substances can be classified with a high, medium or low priority (van Asselt et al., 2018a; van Asselt et al., 2018b). The classification is carried out on the basis of risks for food safety (probability x effect). The criteria are reproduced in table 1. The accompanying decision trees can be found in annex 1. In this advice only decision tree I and decision tree III are used. Substances classified with high priority deserve more attention within the monitoring programme than substances classified medium or low. Over the past few years, BuRO has already advised the Netherlands Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority (NVWA) on the structure of the NPR and on the layout of the monitoring (BuRO, 2018;2019;2020;2022).

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Table 1. Criteria in decision trees that are used to classify substances on the basis of food safety risks.

Criteria used in the decision trees	Group I prohibited substances	Group III authorised veterinary medicinal products
Is there an action limit, MRL/ML ⁵ ?		X
Limit exceeded in the last 5 years	X	X
Use (or probability thereof)	X	X
Scientific information about risks to humans	X	
Length of waiting period		X
Limit exceeded in animal feed in the last 5 years		
Transfer of substance to animal product		
Essential for human application?		X

In response to the WFSR study and the BuRO advice and in advance of the coming into effect of Regulation (EU) 2017/625, the National Residues Plan working group of the NVWA asked BuRO to issue "advice on how the NPR can be restructured in a risk-oriented manner, taking into account the space afforded by the new Official Control Regulation (EU) 2017/625 and the previously issued advice from WFSR." In 2019, BuRO first published an advice in which the above question was answered (BuRO, 2019) Additional advice followed in 2020 and 2022 (BuRO, 2020;2022). In the current advice, the substance groups from the appendix to the draft Regulation (EU) 2017/625 (2.0 SANTE 2017 11987 Annex rev 9) were classified in combination with the animals/animal products aquaculture, farmed game (including rabbit) and honey, that had not previously been considered.

Tables 2 and 3 provide an overview of substance groups and animals/animal products addressed in the previous sets of advice and the current advice.

⁵ Statutory limit for levels in food products. MRL: Maximum Residue Limit for residues of veterinary medicinal products; ML: Maximum Limit for environmental contaminants.

One of the selection criteria in the decision trees is the actual use of agents. To obtain this information, BuRO contacted the Netherlands Veterinary Medicines Institute (SDa) and the trade association of Manufacturers and Importers of Veterinary Medicines (FIDIN). SDa supplied the requested information relating to rabbits directly to WFSR. FIDIN was unable to provide the requested data because only a limited number of agents are registered for bees and there are no registrations for the other investigated animal types. These animals may be treated via the cascade regulation, but FIDIN has no information about this.

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For a risk-oriented structure, the focus of the advice is on the choice of substances according to the classification on the basis of the decision trees.

In this advice, no statement is issued regarding the quality of samples that should be taken per substance group. The number of samples per animal type is laid down in the draft delegated regulation underlying Regulation (EU) 2017/625.

Findings

- Figures 1 to 3 provide an overview per substance group of the number of substances classified low, medium or high for aquaculture, farmed game, rabbit and honey (for the classification of all individual substances see the underlying report from WFSR (Pikkemaat et al., 2022)). For a number of substances (Figure 3), it is concluded that a survey into the use of the substances is needed, before classification is possible.

Figure 1. An overview of the number of low, medium or high classified substances from group A1a (not authorised stilbenes), group A1c (not authorised steroids) and group A2 (prohibited substances).

High #1: means that substances are not formally authorised in countries outside the European Union from which the Netherlands imports animal products, but Internet research revealed that use is considered possible, on the basis of Internet forums and publications.

High #2: means that products were available on the Internet but that their use as veterinary medicinal product is considered unlikely (for example the administration of injections to bees).

High #3: means that MRLs were identified for substances in relevant countries. This shows that veterinary medicinal products could be available.

Figure 2. Overview of the number of low, medium or high classified substances from group A3a (not authorised colourings), group A3b (not authorised antiparasitic agents), group A3c (not authorised antimicrobial agents), group A3d (not authorised coccidiostats), group A3e

(not authorised protein and peptide hormones), group A3f (not authorised sedatives and not authorised NSAIDs).

High #1: means that substances are not formally authorised in countries outside the European Union from which the Netherlands imports animal products, but Internet research revealed that use is considered possible, on the basis of Internet forums and publications.

High #2: means that products were available on the Internet but that their use as veterinary medicinal product is considered unlikely (for example the administration of injections to bees).

High #3: means that MRLs were identified for substances in relevant countries. This shows that veterinary medicinal products could be available.

High #4: means registered products for pet animals have been found and that indications for use have been found via literature study or via products available online.

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Figure 3. Overview of the number of low, medium or high classified substances from group B1a (authorised antibiotics), group B1b (authorised antiparasitic agents), group B1c (authorised sedatives), group B1d (authorised NSAIDs), group B1e (other authorised substances) and group B2 (authorised coccidiostats).

Start survey means that at present no monitoring data for a substance are available because they are not included in the National Residues Plan. If the final outcome is start survey without further addition, no indications have been found that the substance is potentially being used.

Start survey*1 means that Internet research suggested potential use. A survey into the use of this substance in this animal type is recommended.

Start survey*2 means that non-compliant results were identified in poultry. This suggests possible use in game poultry. A survey into the use of this substance in this animal type is recommended. If a substance is classified both as Start survey*1 and Start survey*2 (in other words if Internet research has indicated potential use and there were non-compliant results in poultry), they are counted in this figure in the final category.

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Findings (continued)

- For the majority of veterinary medicinal products, monitoring data for the animals/animal products from this advice are absent.
- Due to a lack of data, it was not possible to classify veterinary medicinal products in the insect production chain. There are two routes via which veterinary medicinal products could make their way into this production chain: via contaminated substrates or through the administration of veterinary medicinal products for prevention or treatment of health problems. The latter option is grounds for concern because at present no veterinary medicinal products are authorised for use in insects.
- There are no registered veterinary medicinal products for use in farmed game, so that veterinary medicinal products for this group are always prescribed via the cascade regulation.
- The animals/animal products addressed in this advice do not belong to the large animal production chains in the Netherlands. As a consequence, the majority of the products are imported from countries where other rules may apply to the use of veterinary medicinal products, as a consequence of which other veterinary medicinal products can be identified.
- The list of substances included in this study is broader than the list of substances as specified in the draft implementing regulation. The list has been kept consistent with the previous assessments in other animal types. Reasons for the use of substances outside the implementing regulation may be use of the cascade regulation (farmed game, rabbits), the large proportion of import (aquaculture, rabbits) from countries with a different approach to the use of veterinary medicinal products or lack of knowledge (hobby beekeepers).

Answer to the question

How can the NPR be restructured in a risk-oriented manner, taking into account the space afforded by the new Official Control Regulation (EU) 2017/625 and the previously issued advice by RIKILT?

The tables drawn up by WFSR with low, medium or high classification can be used for a risk-oriented choice of substances for the structuring of the NPR by the directorate Inspection of the NVWA.

The NPR can be structured in a risk-oriented manner, in respect of choice of substances, by opting for chemical substance-animal or chemical substance-animal product combinations classified by WFSR as high and medium. For the classification of all individual substances, see Pikkemaat et al., 2022.

Advice from BuRO

To the Head of Agency

- Use the classification of chemical substance-animal or chemical substance-animal product combination as reported in the advice for a risk-oriented substance choice in structuring the NPR. Pay specific attention to imported products.
- At regular intervals, for example every three years, evaluate both the composition of the list of substances and the classification of the substance-animal/animal product combination.
- Focus on making structural agreements with FIDIN and SDa in the field of data interchange.

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Yours sincerely,

Office for Risk Assessment & Research
Prof. Antoon Opperhuizen

Appendix 1. Decision trees

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Group I - Prohibited substances

Decision tree (prohibited substances) relating to table 1 in which the criteria for the classification of substances are included.

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Group III - Authorised substances EU

Decision tree (authorised veterinary medicinal products) relating to table 1 in which the criteria for the classification of substances are included.

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